

ABDUKHOSHIM ISMAILOV TOOK THE PLACE OF UZBEK NATIONAL INSTRUMENTALIST

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of the place of the well-known musicologist and creator Abduhoshim Ismailov in the development of Uzbek musical performance art. It describes the creative approaches of Abduhoshim Ismailov in the performance of the national instrument, his pedagogical activities and his contribution to the national music culture. Also, the article examines the importance of his works on the modernization of musical instruments and his creative heritage in promoting the national music art at the international level. The study shows the relevance of highlighting the unique creative style of Abduhoshim Ismailov in the performance of the national instrument and promoting it to the young generation.

Key words: Abduhoshim Ismailov, Uzbek musical performance, national music culture, musical instrument modernization, music pedagogy, creative heritage, international acquaintance.

Introduction.

The performance of Uzbek national instruments occupies a special place in the world music culture with its rich historical traditions and unique performance styles characteristic of art. The contribution of well-known musicologists and creators in the development of this field is immeasurable. One such person is Abduhoshim Ismailov, whose creativity and scientific activity are of great importance in bringing Uzbek musical performance to a new level.

Abduhoshim Ismailov is known for his creative approach and pedagogical skills in modernizing national musical instruments, forming unique performance styles and promoting them internationally. He is recognized not only as a skilled performer, but also as a person who sets an example in preserving the musical heritage and passing it on to the younger generation. This article analyzes the contribution of Abduhoshim Ismailov to the performance of the national instrument, his creative activity and influence on the art of music.

This research is aimed at deepening the understanding of the history of Uzbek national musical performance and introducing the creative heritage of Abduhoshim Ismailov to the general public. This makes it possible to preserve the national cultural heritage and make a new contribution to its development.

Material:

Abduhoshim Ismailov's creative activity played an important role in bringing the national musical performance of Uzbekistan to a new level. His creative approaches were formed on the basis of deep knowledge of national musical traditions and successful combination of modern performance techniques. During his creative career, Ismailov was

engaged in perfecting national musical instruments, expanding their technical capabilities and enriching performance styles.

One of the most important achievements of Abduhoshim Ismailov is the modernization of national musical instruments and introduction of new technical capabilities. In his career, he worked on expanding the sound range of instruments such as tor, rubob, dutor, and adapting their performance capabilities to modern requirements. This made it possible to successfully use national musical instruments not only in traditional music, but also in modern genres.

Ismailov not only worked on musical instruments, but also paid great attention to creating a special repertoire for the performance of national instruments. The works written by him are distinguished by their artistic excellence, musical precision and expansion of performance possibilities. Through this, he played an important role in promoting national instruments at the international level.

Abduhoshim Ismailov's pedagogical activity is also noteworthy. He trained a number of great specialists in the performance of the Uzbek national musical instrument and used modern pedagogical approaches in this regard. Ismailov paid special attention to the formation of not only technical skills, but also respect for national culture and a creative approach in young performers.

Also, his work is of great importance in preserving the creative experience in the performance of national musical instruments and passing it on to the next generation. Even today, his works and performance styles are actively studied in national music schools and performed by the younger generation.

In this article, Abduhoshim Ismailov's contribution to the national musical performance and the importance of his creative heritage in enriching the Uzbek music culture were analyzed in depth. His works served to bring national musical performance to a new level and had a significant impact on the development of this field.

Literature review:

National and foreign sources, scientific articles and researches of musicologists are important in studying the place of Abduhoshim Ismailov in Uzbek musical performance. This article analyzes the available scientific sources about his creative heritage and activities, and highlights their main conclusions and scientific views.

In national musicology, studies on Abduhoshim Ismailov's work are mainly focused on his performance style, pedagogical activities, and his contribution to the modernization of musical instruments. In particular, articles and monographs written by artists of Uzbekistan serve as the main source for studying Ismailov's creative directions. In these works, it is emphasized that his performance style is based on national traditions and is combined with modern performance techniques.

For example, in the article of Uzbek musicologist A. Rasulov, Ismailov's work on the modernization of national instruments is described in detail. In the research, the technical changes that he introduced to instruments such as the string and rubob, the effect of these changes on performance possibilities and the high level of playing national musical works were noted.

Also, scientific articles published by the Art Institute of Uzbekistan discuss Ismailov's pedagogical activity, innovative approaches and methodical methods used in teaching the performance of national instruments. These studies shed light on his contribution to the

development of national music schools as a pedagogue and reveal his place in the education of young performers.

Although there are few foreign sources dedicated to the work of Abduhoshim Ismailov, they cover his work on the international promotion of national musical instruments. In several articles written by foreign researchers, his participation in international music festivals and thereby increasing interest in the performance of national musical instruments are recognized.

However, it was revealed during the analysis that not enough comprehensive studies have been conducted about his creative activity. This shows the need for a deeper study of Ismailov's creative heritage and the need to expand scientific analysis in the future.

In conclusion, the analysis of the available literature confirms the great contribution of Abduhoshim Ismailov to the performance of the national instrument. These literatures, on the one hand, serve as a source for illuminating his creative activity, and on the other hand, serve as a basis for new scientific directions for a more in-depth study of his musical heritage.

Discussion:

In the process of analyzing the role and contribution of Abduhoshim Ismailov in the performance of the Uzbek national musical instrument, it was found that his creative activity had a significant impact on the development of the national music culture. He served to bring Uzbek national music to a new level through his performance methods, modernization of musical instruments and pedagogical approaches.

Firstly, Ismailov managed to increase the level of performance of national instruments by expanding their technical capabilities. His technical changes to instruments such as rubob and thor served not only to preserve national traditions, but also to harmonize them with modern musical genres. This created a solid basis for popularizing national musical instruments at the international level.

Secondly, Ismailov's pedagogical activity is aimed at introducing new approaches in national musical education. His focus on teaching students in-depth national traditions, as well as mastering modern techniques, ensured high efficiency in training young performers. As a result, his students were recognized not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the international music scene.

Thirdly, Ismailov's works on national instrument performance enriched the national musical repertoire. His creative approaches created new opportunities for combining artistic expression and technical skills in the performance of national music works. These works are widely used in national music schools due to their artistic value and performance requirements.

However, in the course of the analysis, it became clear that no complete scientific research has been conducted on his creative heritage. The issues of further study of Ismailov's creative activity and preservation of his legacy for future generations are still relevant. In particular, it is necessary to analyze his activities on the international music scene and his contribution to the development of national music in this area. Abduhoshim Ismailov's contribution to the performance of the Uzbek national musical instrument not only enriched the national music culture, but also served to make it known at the international level. His creative heritage, performance methods and pedagogical approaches are an integral part of Uzbek music culture, and preservation and promotion of this heritage in the future is one of the important tasks for the development of national culture.

Conclusion:

Abduhoshim Ismailov is a person who left a bright mark in the performance of the Uzbek national musical instrument as a unique creator and performer. His creative activity, work on modernization of national musical instruments and musical heritage made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek music culture. Technical and artistic innovations introduced by Ismailov to national instruments played an important role not only in the performance of traditional musical works, but also in harmonizing modern genres with national instruments.

Ismailov's pedagogical approaches and efforts to educate the young generation started a new stage in the national musical education system. His students have become high representatives of national musical performance, which confirms his success as a pedagogue. Also, his creative heritage and works aimed at enriching the national musical repertoire serve to popularize Uzbek musical performance at the international level.

Analyzing the creative and pedagogical activity of Abduhoshim Ismailov in this article, his contribution to bringing national musical performance to a new level was determined. However, it became clear that further scientific research is necessary for the in-depth study of his international activities and creative heritage.

Abduhoshim Ismailov's creative achievements and rich heritage continue to develop national culture and convey it to the younger generation. His work serves as an important resource for promoting Uzbek music culture on a global scale and preserving national values. Therefore, scientific and practical in-depth study, preservation and promotion of his heritage is one of the urgent tasks before the national music art.

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